

Self-esteem, Loneliness and Depression in Adolescents whose Parents Divorced

Abednego

Saragihabednego0@gmail.com

Gunadarma University, Jakarta, Indonesia.

Abstract.

The purpose of this study was to empirically examine the effect of self-esteem, loneliness on depression in adolescents whose parents are divorced. While the respondents in this study were adolescents who had divorced parents. The sample of this study amounted to 79 participants aged 12-21 years. This study uses multiple linear regression methods so that it can predict the relationship between variables and uses purposive sampling techniques. The scales used in this study are Rosenberg Self- Esteem Scale (SES), UCLA Loneliness Scale Version 3, and Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) The results showed that there was an effect of self-esteem on depression by 39%, while the effect of loneliness on depression was 43.7%, and there was an effect of self-esteem and loneliness on depression in adolescents whose parents were divorced by 54.3%.

Keywords:

self-esteem, loneliness, depression, adolescents, divorce.

Adolescence is a transitional phase from childhood to adulthood. The transition process causes physical, cognitive and psychosocial changes. This phase is very important for adolescents because there is a process of sexual maturity (Papalia & Martorell, 2014). This can affect emotions in adolescents to be unstable or changeable. In this phase, the presence of parents is needed in guiding adolescents to develop properly.

The presence of parents in providing affective support, such as providing warmth, loving and being loved, and mutual respect is an effort by parents in guiding their developing teenage children towards adulthood (Rahman, 2015). Warmth in the family is very important, but not all families are harmonious. Problems in the family

sometimes occur such as domestic violence, and economic problems due to increasing needs but little income can trigger divorce (Matondang, 2014). The condition of divorced families and adolescents who are experiencing emotional turmoil makes adolescents carry two burdens simultaneously. Some cases of parental divorce can affect the lives of teenagers because they have not fully accepted the circumstances of their parents' divorce. Divorce makes adolescents potentially experience academic failure, eating disorders and sleep disorders, depression, suicide, precociousness, drugs, lack of responsibility, guilt and anger (Stahl, 2004). In addition, divorce can cause adolescents to receive less attention and care from parents, experience sexual violence, loneliness, avoidance, making adolescents whose parents divorce at risk of psychological disorders such as depression (Schaan, Schulz, Schachinger, & Vogele, 2019).

Depression in Latin *deprimere* which can be interpreted as pressing down. Depression is not only about feelings, thoughts, difficulty concentrating, difficulty sleeping but more than that it can affect all aspects of human life (Gilbert, 2001). Cases of depression in Indonesia increase every year, there are around 35 million people affected by depression. (WHO, 2016). Depression in adolescents not only shows sadness but irritable behavior, boredom or inability to feel pleasure (Papalia and Martorell, 2014). Depressive conditions in adolescents are influenced by low levels of self-esteem due to parental divorce.

According to Clarke (2011) self-esteem is an individual's view of himself and his view is also recognized by others. In addition, self-esteem is a belief in the ability to think to overcome the basic challenges of life and the belief to succeed, be happy and enjoy the results of efforts (Branden, 2011). Self-esteem includes three dimensions, namely social trust, learning ability and physical appearance as indicators of self-esteem in adolescents (Zhou, Li, Tian, & Huebner, 2020). If these three things are lacking in adolescents, it will cause low self-esteem. Family dysfunction can make an adolescent have low self-esteem. Adolescents who have divorced parents have low self-esteem compared to adolescents whose parents are not divorced (Istiana, 2017). When adolescent self-esteem is positive, it will become optimism and self-confidence. Conversely, if adolescents' self-esteem is low, they can experience depression. Low self-esteem is central to the development of depression in adolescents (Zhou, Li, Tian, & Huebner, 2020). In addition, based on research by Isik, Başoğul, and Yildirim (2020), the experience of depression can be affected by loneliness.

Loneliness is a feeling of emptiness and an experience of solitude that results from a lack of intimacy in the family (Gibson, 2015). Adolescents whose

parents are divorced will lose an intimate relationship with one parent and experience a void. In addition, loneliness is a painful emotional experience and can affect quality of life (Margalit, 2010). Loneliness can occur due to lack of parental attention to adolescents who have to carry the burden alone and without help from parents, this can make adolescents experience depression (Erzen & Çikrikci, 2018).

Based on the explanation previously described, the hypothesis of this study is that self-esteem and loneliness can explain depression in adolescents whose parents are divorced.

METHOD

This study is a qualitative study with participants in this study are adolescents aged 12-21 years and have divorced parents. The research participants consisted of 100 people including 72 women and 28 men. Participants consisted of students to college students.

In this study, the scale used to measure self-esteem uses the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (SES). In the SES scale there are 10 items that make up the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (SES) designed to optimize ease of administration and time savings. One example of an item in this scale is "I feel that I am a valuable person, at least on par with others". The answer options consist of 1-4 starting from never to always. The reliability of this scale is 0.86.

In this study, researchers measured loneliness using the UCLA Loneliness Scale Version 3 (Russell, 1996). There are 20 ULS items used to measure loneliness with a reliability of 0.89. One example of an item on this scale is "how often do you not have friends?". The answer options range from 1-4 ranging from never to always.

The depression scale in this study uses the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) used to measure depression (Beck, Epstein, Brown, & Steer, 1988). There are 10 BDI items with a reliability of 0.89. One example of an item on this scale is "I don't feel sad".

DATA ANALYSIS

This study used simple data analysis techniques with multiple linear regression tests to test the effect of the variables of self-esteem (X1), loneliness (X2), and depression (Y) of adolescents using SPSS version 25.

RESULTS

Based on the results of the study, it is known that regression results were carried out to see the effect of self-esteem and loneliness on depression in adolescents.

Table 1. Regression Test Results of Self Esteem on Depression

F	Sig	R Square
49,284	0.000	0.390

The results of simple regression analysis show that the F value is 49.284 and the significance coefficient is $0.000 \leq 0.050$. This shows that there is an influence of self-esteem on depression in adolescents whose parents divorce. In addition, it is known that the R square value is 0.390, which means that self-esteem affects depression by 39%, while an influence of 61% is obtained from other variables that cannot be explained in this study.

Table 2. Regression Test Results of Loneliness on Depression

F	Sig	R Square
59,852	0.000	0.437

The simple regression results show that the F value is 59.852 and the significance coefficient is $0.000 \leq 0.050$. This shows that there is an influence of loneliness on depression in adolescents whose parents are divorced. In addition, it is known that the R square value is 0.437, which means that loneliness affects depression by 43.7%, while an influence of 56.3% is obtained from other variables that cannot be explained in this study.

Table 3. Regression Test Results of Self Esteem and Loneliness on Depression

F	Sig	R Square
45,169	0.000	0.543

Then, the results of the analysis in table 3. Shows the significance of regression between self-esteem and loneliness on depression, together in a study of $0.000 \leq 0.050$, this shows that there is a significant influence between self-esteem and loneliness on depression in adolescents. The R square value is 0.543. This shows that self-esteem and loneliness have an influence on depression by 54.3%.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of this study, it can be seen that self-esteem and anxiety are factors that influence the occurrence of depression in adolescents whose parents are divorced. In this study, it was found that loneliness has a greater influence than self-esteem on depression.

Loneliness has an influence on depression by 43.7%. This can happen because loneliness in a person, whether young or elderly, can lead to depressive experiences. This is supported by research by Erzen and Çikrikci (2018), regarding the analysis conducted on several research results regarding loneliness and depression from year to year it was found that no changes occurred so it can be concluded that loneliness is a permanent factor in the occurrence of depression. Affection and attention from parents is very influential on adolescent development, therefore divorce can have positive and negative impacts on adolescents. (Ramadhani & Krisnani, 2019). Loneliness is a negative impact of divorce that can be felt directly. When divorce occurs there is a change where the house becomes quieter than before and the loss of communication with parents. This condition occurs in adolescents whose parents divorce who experience unpreparedness for losing attention and communication with one of the closest people, namely their parents (Wulandari & Fauziah, 2019). In addition, loneliness in adolescents caused by divorce makes the disconnection or interaction in the family so that parents and children live in one house but seem to have their own lives (Rahmawati, 2019). Conditions like this that make adolescents experience loneliness in their lives. Loneliness and protracted sadness due to parental divorce can make adolescents experience depression. This is supported by research by Fadilah (2017), that the higher the loneliness in adolescents, the higher the likelihood of adolescents experiencing depression. In adolescent life there are factors that can cause depression, one of which is self-esteem.

Self-esteem has an effect of 39% on depression in adolescents. For each individual, self-esteem is important because it relates to how individuals value themselves. Many factors can affect adolescent self-esteem, such as economic status and family status. It is proven that good relationships within the family can foster feelings of security and acceptance so that adolescents can have positive self-esteem (Hidayati, 2016). Poor family relationships due to divorce can have an impact on adolescent self-esteem because family divorce makes adolescents feel different from other adolescents who have complete families, therefore, this can make adolescent self-

esteem negative. This is proven through research by Istiana (2017) which states that the self-esteem of adolescents whose parents are divorced is lower than adolescents whose parents are not divorced. Negative self-esteem in adolescents can occur such as blaming themselves for parental divorce, feeling that life is unfair and feeling worthless. Negative self-esteem in adolescents can lead to depression. This is in accordance with research by Khan (2012), which states that adolescents who have negative self-esteem tend to experience depression compared to adolescents who have positive self-esteem. Negative self-esteem is a factor that can make adolescents experience depression. In addition, self-esteem and loneliness influence the occurrence of depression in adolescents.

Self-esteem and loneliness have an influence on depression by 54.3%. These two factors have an influence on the occurrence of depression in adolescents whose parents are divorced. The results of this study are supported by previous research stating that self-esteem and loneliness have an influence on depression. The lower or negative the self-esteem of adolescents, the higher the depression and if loneliness is high, depression is high (Yusuf, 2016). The condition of divorced parents makes adolescents inferior or insecure, moody, have no hope in life. This is a negative self-esteem that will later make adolescents depressed (Afrina & Hasanah, 2019). Depression can also occur in adolescents who experience loneliness. Lack of attention, experience of rejection, loss of communication with family makes loneliness in adolescents (Utami, Ahamad and Ifdil, 2017). Adolescents whose parents divorce can experience several factors that can encourage depression. In this study, it was found that, negative self-esteem and loneliness affect depression in adolescents whose parents are divorced.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the analysis, it shows that self-esteem and loneliness affect depression in adolescents whose parents are divorced. Self-esteem and loneliness are factors that can cause individuals to experience depression. Negative self-esteem due to parental divorce can encourage conditions of worthlessness and self-blame that make adolescents depressed. While loneliness is an inevitable effect of parental divorce that forces adolescents to lose communication with parents and withdraw. Both factors can affect depression in adolescents whose parents are divorced.

SUGGESTIONS

Some suggestions can be given for further research. First, future researchers can conduct research by testing other factors outside the variables of this study because it is necessary to know other factors that affect depression in adolescents whose parents divorce. Second, if researchers will examine the same variables, they should be able to increase the number of respondents more than this study so that the results are more valid and reliable.

REFERENCES

- Afrina, D., Hasanah, N. (2019). Studi kasus self-esteem pada remaja yang orang tuanya broken home di SMP Dharma Patra p. brandan. *Jurnal Serunai Bimbingan dan Konseling*, 8(2), 107-116.
- Beck, A. T., Epstein, N., Brown, G., & Steer, R. A. (1988). Sebuah inventori untuk mengukur kecemasan klinis: Sifat-sifat psikometrik. *Jurnal Konsultasi dan Psikologi Klinis*, 56(6), 893-897. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-006X.56.6.893>
- Branden, N. (2011). Cara meningkatkan harga diri Anda: Pendekatan berorientasi tindakan yang telah terbukti untuk meningkatkan rasa hormat dan kepercayaan diri. New York: Bantam Books.
- Clarke, J. I. (2011). Harga Diri Sebuah Urusan Keluarga. Minnesota: Hazeiden Publishing.
- Erzen, E., & Çikrikci, Ö. (2018). Pengaruh kesepian terhadap depresi: Sebuah meta-analisis. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*, 64(5), 427-435. doi:10.1177/0020764018776349
- Fadillah, E. Y. (2017). Hubungan Kesepian Dengan Depresi Yang Di Moderatori Oleh Religiusitas Pada Anak Yatim Pondok Anak Yatim (PAY) As Salman, Malang. *Psikodimensia*, 16(2), 144-120.
- Gilbert, P. (2001). Mengatasi depresi: Pendekatan langkah demi langkah untuk mendapatkan kendali atas depresi. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Hidayati, N. W. (2016). Hubungan harga diri dan konformitas teman sebaya dengan kenakalan remaja. *Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan Indonesia*, 1(2).

- Isik, K., Baçoğul, C., & Yildirim, H. (2020). Hubungan antara kesepian yang dirasakan dan depresi pada lansia dan faktor-faktor yang mempengaruhinya. Perspektif dalam Perawatan Psikiatri. doi:10.1111/ppc.12572.
- Istiana. (2017). Perbedaan Harga Diri Remaja Ditinjau Dari Status Keluarga Pada Sma Al - Ulum Medan. Jurnal Psikologi Konseling. Vol. 1, No. 1, 1-10.
- Khan, R. I. (2012). Perilaku asertif, harga diri dan kecenderungan depresi. Persona: Jurnal Psikologi Indonesia, 1(2).
- Margalit, M. (2010). Anak-anak dan remaja yang kesepian: Persepsi diri, pengucilan sosial, dan harapan. Dalam Anak dan Remaja yang Kesepian: Persepsi Diri, Pengucilan Sosial, dan Harapan. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-6284-3>
- Matondang, A. (2014). Faktor-faktor yang mengakibatkan perceraian dalam perkawinan. JPPUMA Jurnal Ilmu Pemerintahan dan Sosial Politik Universitas Medan Area, 2(2), 141-150.
- Papalia, D. E., Feldman, R. D., Martorel, G. (2014). Experience Human Development. [Menyelami Perkembangan Manusia]. (Alih Bahasa: F. W. Herarti). (Edisi Kedua belas). Jakarta: Salemba Humanika
- Rahmawati, D. (2019). Pemodelan Remaja Putri Korban Perceraian Hidup Dengan Ayah. Jurnal Riset Mahasiswa Bimbingan Dan Konseling, 5(3), 236-241.
- Ramadhani, P. E., & Krisnani, H. (2019). Analisis Dampak Perceraian Orang Tua Terhadap Anak Remaja. Fokus: Jurnal Pekerjaan Sosial, 2(1), 109-119.
- Russell, D. W. (1996). Skala Kesepian UCLA (Versi 3): Reliabilitas, validitas, dan struktur faktor. Jurnal penilaian kepribadian, 66(1), 20-40.
- Schaan, V. K., Schulz, A., Schächinger, H., & Vögele, C. (2019). Perceraian orang tua dikaitkan dengan peningkatan risiko gangguan mental pada perempuan. Jurnal Gangguan Afektif, 257, 91-99. doi: 10.1016/j.jad.2019.06.071
- Stahl, P. M. (2004). Mengasuh anak setelah perceraian. Jakarta: Penerbit PT Gramedia Widiasarana Indonesia.
- Starosta, A. J., & Brenner, L. A. (2018). Inventarisasi Kecemasan Beck (Beck Anxiety Inventory). In Encyclopedia of Clinical Neuropsychology. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-57111-9_1972

- Utami, D. R., Ahmad, R., & Ifdil, I. (2017). Tingkat Kesenian Remaja di Panti Asuhan X Kota Padang. *JURNAL KONSELING GUSJIGANG*, 3(1).
- Wulandari, D., & Fauziah, N. (2019). Pengalaman Remaja Korban Broken Home (Studi Kualitatif Fenomenologis). *Empati*, 8(1), 1-9.
- Yen, C. F., Yang, P., Wu, Y.-Y., & Cheng, C.-P. (2013). Hubungan Antara Kesulitan Keluarga dan Kecemasan Sosial di Kalangan Remaja di Taiwan. *The Journal of Nervous and Mental Disease*.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/nmd.0000000000000032>
- Yusuf, N. P. (2016). Hubungan harga diri dan kesepian dengan depresi pada remaja. In *Seminar ASEAN 2nd Psychology & Humanity, Forum Psikologi UMM* (pp. 19-20).
- Zhou, J., Li, X., Tian, L., & Huebner, E. S. (2018). Hubungan longitudinal antara harga diri rendah dan depresi pada remaja awal: Peran sensitivitas penolakan dan kesepian. *Psikologi dan Psikoterapi: Teori, Penelitian dan Praktik*, 93(1), 54-71. doi: 10.1111/papt.12207